

CORRELATION STUDY OF PERSONALITY AND INTEREST OF SCHOOL PUPILS

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Abstract:

The present research study is intended to ascertain the level of correlation existing among two Variables, viz .Personality and Interest of Secondary school students. The sample mobilized for the research study consisted of 1,440 secondary school students. The research data related to students' interests and personality were procured by using two standardized research tools The statistical techniques such as Pearson product moment Correlation and statistical significance of coefficients of correlation were used for drawing out the conclusion.

There is significant relationship between the personality and interest of school pupils.

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Key words : Personality, Interest, Correlation

Background of the Research Study :

It is wonderful that new thoughts, new theories, modern trends and strategies have emerged in educational sphere and system. Yet, the educational objective that has remained intact, and that has been preserved for centuries, is related to proper and balanced development of human personality. One of the significant aspects of personality is interest. Since interest is intimately related to individual's personality, he or she naturally gets motivation, energy, will power and determination in undertaking various activities. Proper interests contribute to development and integration of personality. So it is clear that personality creates and promotes interests.

In Indian democratic state, balanced and all round development of personality is looked upon as the obligation of the state and the right of the citizens. It is evident that the national progress, prosperity and excellence are closely linked with the quality of its citizens—their educational level, cultural and ethical values, industriousness and democratic outlook. Personality development, indeed, is a must for Indian democracy.

Interest acts as a powerful source of energy that prompts an individual to action. It is always accompanied by mental satisfaction and pleasant emotions. It provides motivation, energy, determination, will power and pleasure in doing activities in the areas of one's interest. If the students are aware of their interests, if they are made known to the students, if interests are determined scientifically, students will be able to go in for proper education and profession and excel in them by utilizing their personality traits.

All students have general education and similar curricula up to std. X. Thereafter, they are required to select specific discipline and think about future profession which they do generally on the basis of their aspirations. Since there are numerous fields of education and professions in this era of technology, they need to make selections rather carefully. For progress and excellence in education and profession, it becomes essential to consider student's personality, educational and vocational interest. It is also necessary to know the relationships between them. With these thoughts and approach, this research study was completed.

This study which was meticulously planned, and accurately executed, has revealed reliable findings about interrelations between two research variables. These findings have significant implications for academicians, school teachers, parents and students who need to strive hard, hand in hand for harmonious development of student personality, inculcation of proper interests.

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE RESEARCH STUDY

'India shall emerge as Super Power in near future.' These are the prophetic words of many western and Indian thinkers. This prophecy suggests sky-high quality improvements in education, technology, industrial infrastructure, production pattern and general mental framework of Indian citizens. What is really wonderful is that the prophesy is slowly turning out to be a reality. One needs to realize that the thinkers when they predict these improvements, they base their predictions on ever-increasing quality of people and citizens. The quality of citizens, no doubt, depends on the ethical values cherished by them, and the life-style molded by the noble cultural values. But it also depends to a great extent on the education and efficiency of citizens. The citizens who contribute with all their might to the national economy, contribute to the national growth, development and well-being. India has been witnessing a tremendous spread of education and notable enhancement in its quality. When the citizens enter into professions and vocations suitable to their personality characteristics and interests, they are more likely to render yeoman services for promoting the cause of national and social welfare. This research is significant from this standpoint. It provides a direction for student's future education and vocations that are in tune

with their mental characteristics and total personality.

To sum up, this research study is significant for students, parents, schools and teachers, and society. It has psychological significance as well. The students are the direct, and parents, teachers and society are the indirect beneficiaries of this research study.

I. Statement of the Problem

The present study is designed to investigate into the relationships among pupils' personality and interests with a view to provide guidance, recommendations and suggestions for educational counselling.

The research problem is entitled as '**A Study of Correlation between Personality and Interests of School Pupils**'.

II. Definition of Specific Terms

Personality

It is the sum total and dynamic organization within the individual of the psycho-physical systems such as physical, mental, social and temperamental. It is the unique quality of human adjustment and behavior.

Interest

It is a disposition of an individual. It is influenced by innate tendencies and acquired habits. It is a unique personal feeling involving oneness between the individual and the object of liking.

III. Objectives of the Study

- a. To find out the correlation between pupils' personality and their interest.
- b. To suggest and recommend measures for pupils' educational guidance and counselling.

IV. Methodology of Study

The Descriptive research (quantitative) method was used as it best suited the nature and the objectives of the present research study. Koul, I. (1990) has further classified the descriptive studies into three categories (p.404).of these categories, the present research is an interrelationship study. This category has been further classified into four subcategories (p.416) of those subcategories; the present research belongs to the Correlation and Prediction Study subcategory.

V. Variables of the study

There are two variables Personality and Interest.

VI. Tools for Data Collection

Personality was measured by "High School Personality Questionnaire" developed by Cattell, R.B. The "Educational Interest Record"(EIR) was the standardized by Kulshrestha, S.P. was used for measuring pupils interests.

VII. Population and Sample

The population for the research includes all the secondary school pupils. The sample consisted of 1440 pupils studying in Std. 10th of the Marathi medium schools located in Nashik tahsil. It was drawn from 18 urban schools, 5 rural schools and one post basic ashram school which were selected by probability method viz. simple lottery method.

VIII. Statistical Techniques

Pearson product moment correlation and Statistical significance of coefficients of Correlation (r) was ascertained.

IX. Conclusions

TABLE 1: PRODUCT MOMENT COEFFICIENT OF CORRELATION OF PERSONALITY SCORES WITH THE INTEREST SCORES

NO.	DETAILS	VALUES
1	N	1,295
2	Σ_1	1,81,783
3	Σ_2	76,123
4	Σ_1^2	1,40,39,31,677
5	Σ_2^2	24,68,07,201
6	$\Sigma_{1.2}$	58,57,65,052
		$(r_{1.2}) = 0.9324$

It is clear from the Table 1 that the-

-N i.e. the total number of paired scores is **1,295**

- Σ_1 i.e. the sum of the scores on the interest inventory is **1,81,783**

- Σ_2 i.e. the sum of the scores of student's academic achievement is **76,130**

- Σ_1^2 i.e. the sum of the squared scores on the interest inventory is **1,40,39,31,677**

- Σ_2^2 i.e. the sum of the squared scores of student's academic achievement is **24, 68,07,201.**

- $\Sigma_{1.2}$ i.e. the sum of the products of the paired scores on the personality and the scores of interest inventory is **58,57,65,052.**

The Product-Moment coefficient of correlation of the personality inventory scores with the interest inventory score ($r_{1.2}$) is 0.9324 Therefore, it is clear that there is positive high relationship between the measures of personality and the measures of interests.

It also predicts that if students have excellent and balanced personality, their educational interests

will be excellent and rich. On the contrary, the students with undeveloped or underdeveloped, qualitatively poor and imbalanced personality will not be able to develop proper and strong educational interests.

It is, therefore, concluded that the two variables, viz. personality and the educational interests co-vary, and personality of students is a significant indicator of their educational interests.

TABLE 2: PRODUCT MOMENT COEFFICIENT OF CORRELATION

Sr. No.	Variables for Correlation	Product –Moment Coefficients of Correlation
L	Personality and Interest	$(r_{1,2}) = 0.9324$

- There is very high positive correlation between the personality and interest of pupil.

TABLE 3 : t-CRITICAL VALUE OF PRODUCT – MOMENT COEFFICIENT OF CORRELATION

Sr. No.	Details	Values
L	Coefficient of Correlation between Personality and Interest	$r_{12} = 0.9324$
2	Degree of Freedom (N-2)	1.293
3	level of Significance	0.05
4	t critical value	1.960
5	Observed t critical value	92.87*
Remark: "r" is statistically significant		

(*Significant at 0.05 level)

Table 3 indicates that -

- The Product-Moment coefficient of correlation of the personality measures with the interest measures (r_{12}) is 0.9324,
- For 1,293 degrees of freedom and at the 0.05 level of significance, the t-critical value in the t-distribution table is 1.960 and
- The calculated t-critical value of the Product-Moment coefficient of correlation ($r_{12} = 0.9324$) is 92.878.

Since the calculated t-critical value of 92.878 exceeds the t-critical value of 1.960 given in the t-distribution table, the Product-Moment coefficient of correlation, ($r_{12} = 0.9324$) is accepted as statistically significant at the 0.05 level of significance. Out of hundred replications only in five replications this Product-Moment coefficient of correlation ($r_{12} = 0.9690$) i.e. positive high relationship between the personality and the interest measures is likely to emerge due to chance factors, sampling errors or other reasons.

From this the null hypothesis is rejected. Now it is inferred that there is significant correlation between the personality and interest of pupils.

X. Major finding of the Research:

There is a significant relationship between the personality and the interest of school pupils.

I. Implications of the Findings

The conclusion related to the big and significant Correlation between pupils' personality and their interest indicates that dynamic, organized, integrated and unique personality develops arouses, sustains and regulates proper interests of pupils. Thus, development and inculcation of proper interests is significant for dynamic human personality.

This research study has implications for schools teachers and teacher educators.

The school teachers should contribute to proper and balanced development of student personality. They should identify their student's natural and acquired interests and respect their inborn interest of self-regard. They should provide effective learning experiences for better outcomes in school achievement of pupils.

The teacher educators should create awareness among teacher trainees about this significant interrelationships existing among the three variables. For this purpose, they will have to think of an integrated approach through which correlation nature of pupils' personality, interest and school achievement is explained to the teacher trainees. Even the teacher training institutes need to think of various measures for developing personality of teacher trainees, nourishing their interest in teaching profession and for excellence in scholastic achievements.

This research has an implication for parents as well. If they are conscious how their children's personality, interest and achievements are interrelated, they will be able to channelize their children's energies and mental faculties, and cherish proper expectations about their children.

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